

Dissociation Constants of Diethyldithiocarbamic Acid

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Diethyldithiocarbamic acid was previously reported¹ to be a dibasic one with $pK_{D_1}=7.8$ and $pK_{D_2}=8.4$ (where pK_D terms represent the negative logarithm of the dissociation constants). These values cannot be considered acceptable. The more correct values of pK_{D_1} and pK_{D_2} , obtained by the method of successive approximations, correction term method as well as by other similar methods, have been found to be 7.8 ± 0.1 and 8.0 ± 0.1 respectively.

In our previous investigation¹, sodium diethyldithiocarbamate was titrated against acids and the changes occurring were followed either conductometrically or potentiometrically and diethyldithiocarbamic acid was concluded to be a dibasic one with $pK_{D_1}=7.5$ and $pK_{D_2}=8.4$ (where pK_D terms represent negative logarithm of the dissociation constants). The actual values obtained are shown in Table I. Since $pK_{D_2}-pK_{D_1}$ is less than 3, apparently the values of the dissociation constants are only approximate. Additional procedures are therefore necessary to compute the correct values of pK_{D_1} and pK_{D_2} .

The values of pK_{D_1} and pK_{D_2} must be reasonably constant and their difference should be almost the same. In a system, where $N=2$, pK_D average (determined graphically) must be symmetrically distributed between pK_{D_1} and pK_{D_2} . In Table I, observations F and G may be omitted as the mean values of pK_{D_1} and pK_{D_2} appear to be fairly off the mean values of the other observations. We shall now consider the various procedures to obtain the correct values of the formation constants which are reciprocal of the dissociation constant, $K_D=1/K$, etc.

TABLE I

(Na-diethyldithiocarbamate solution (50 ml) taken and titrated against various acids).

$$\text{Log } K_1 = pK_{D_2} \text{ and } \text{log } K_2 = pK_{D_1}. \quad pK_D = (pK_{D_1} + pK_{D_2})/2$$

No.	Acid used.	pK_{D_1} .	pK_{D_2} .	pK_D .	pK_D from graph.
A	HClO ₄	7.55	8.35	7.95	7.95
B	HClO ₄	7.40	8.20	7.80	7.80
C	HCl	7.60	8.35	7.98	7.95
D	HCl	7.40	8.30	7.85	7.80
E	HCl	7.40	8.40	7.90	7.78
F	HCl	7.70	8.65	8.18	..
G	HAc	7.90	8.75	..	..
H	HAc	7.55	8.25	7.90	7.90
I	HAc	7.65	8.30	7.98	7.95
J	HAc	7.55	8.30	7.88	7.85
K	HAc	7.50	8.30	7.90	7.90

1. Soni and Trivedi, this *Journal*, 1960, 37, 349.

In the method suggested by Bjerrum², equations (1) and (2) are considered to apply even when X , the spreading factor, is not large.

$$K_1 = \frac{1}{(\bar{H})} \text{ when } \bar{n} = 0.5 \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

$$K_2 = \frac{1}{(\bar{H})} \text{ when } \bar{n} = 1.5 \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

K_1 and K_2 obtained in this way are considered temporary constants from which the closer approximations can be made using equations (3) and (4).

$$K_1 = \frac{1}{(\bar{H})} \left\{ \frac{1}{1 + 3K_2(\bar{H})} \right\} \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

$$K_2 = \frac{1}{(\bar{H})} \left\{ 1 + \frac{3}{K_1(\bar{H})} \right\} \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

Now from the graph of $\bar{n}$ against pH , we get approximate values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ at $\bar{n} = 0.5$ and 1.5 , respectively. These values of K_1 and K_2 are to be substituted in equations (3) and (4) and the resulting values are designated as K'_1 and K'_2 . The values of K'_1 and K'_2 , thus obtained, are again substituted in equations (3) and (4) to obtain K''_1 and K''_2 . The procedure is repeated till the successive values of formation constants are nearly constant. This is known as the method of successive approximations (M.S.A.). Table II summarises the data obtained by this method. In the last column, the values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ are rounded up to ± 0.1 unit. This is necessary because pH -meter could be read to ± 0.05 unit and again, the ionic strength of the solution was not maintained constant.

TABLE II

$$\text{Log } K_1 = pK_{D2}, \text{ Log } K_2 = pK_{D1}.$$

No.		Number of approximations					
		0.	1.	2.	3.	4.	5
A	$\log K_1$	8.35	8.18	8.12	8.09	8.08	8.1
	$\log K_2$	7.55	7.72	7.78	7.81	7.82	7.8
B	$\log K_1$	8.20	8.03	7.97	7.94	7.93	7.9
	$\log K_2$	7.40	7.57	7.63	7.66	7.67	7.7
C	$\log K_1$	8.35	8.16	8.09	8.06	8.04	8.0
	$\log K_2$	7.60	7.79	7.86	7.89	7.91	7.8
D	$\log K_1$	8.30	8.16	8.12	8.10	8.10	8.1
	$\log K_2$	7.40	7.54	7.58	7.60	7.60	7.6
E	$\log K_1$	8.40	8.29	8.26	8.25	8.25	8.3
	$\log K_2$	7.40	7.61	7.54	7.55	7.55	7.6
H	$\log K_1$	8.25	8.05	7.96	7.91	7.89	7.9
	$\log K_2$	7.55	7.65	7.84	7.89	7.91	7.9
I	$\log K_1$	8.30	8.08	7.97	7.91	7.88	7.9
	$\log K_2$	7.65	7.87	7.98	8.03	8.07	8.1
J	$\log K_1$	8.20	7.98	7.87	7.82	7.78	7.8
	$\log K_2$	7.55	7.77	7.88	7.93	7.96	8.0
K	$\log K_1$	8.30	8.13	8.07	8.04	8.03	8.0
	$\log K_2$	7.50	7.67	7.73	7.76	7.77	7.8

2. Martell and Calvin, "Chemistry of the Metal Chelate Compounds", 1st ed., 1956, Prentice Hall, Inc., N. J., p. 63.

The method appears not to be successful in the case of observations H, I, and J, as the successive approximations lead to the reversal of the order of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$. It appears that in our case (average value of $\log K = 7.9$) the 'M.S.A.' is successful only when $\Delta f_0 = \log K_1 - \log K_2 \geq 0.8$. As Δf_0 decreases, the 'M.S.A.' appears to be increasingly difficult to apply. Calculations were made, keeping the average value of $\log K$ equal to 7.9 and varying Δf_0 (initial difference between $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$) between 1.0 and 0.2. The data are plotted graphically in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1

In the second method, suggested by Bjerrum, the temporary constants are calculated by employing the values of $\log K$ (read graphically) and 'X', the spreading factor, the latter being the slope at the mid-point of the formation curve. The values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$, obtained in this way may, then be utilised to obtain accurate values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ by M.S.A. Unfortunately this was not possible as M.S.A. could not be applied when Δf_0 was less than 0.8. Hence this method does not appear suitable in the present case. This may again be due to errors in measuring the slope of the graph³. Table III records the data in the case of some of the observations.

TABLE III

No.	X.	$\log K_1 \pm 0.1$.	$\log K_2 \pm 0.1$.	$\log K_3 \pm 0.1$.
A	0.793	8.0	8.2	7.8
B	0.799	7.8	8.0	7.6
C	0.799	8.0	8.2	7.8
Mean		7.9	8.1	7.7

Irving and Rossetti⁴ as well as Rossetti and Rossetti⁵ have discussed in detail the methods for computing successive formation constants from the experimental data. The two additional methods suggested by Irving and Rossetti will now be considered.

Correction Term Method⁴

In a system, where $N = 2$, the theoretical formation curve is symmetrical about the mid-point. At $N = 2$, the following equation may be obtained:

$$\bar{\alpha} + K_1 H (\bar{\alpha} - 1) + 4K_1 K_2 (H)^2. (\bar{\alpha} - 2) = 0 \quad \dots \quad (5)$$

3. Rossetti and Rossetti, "The Determination of Stability Constants," 1st ed., 1961, McGraw Hill Book Co., N.Y., p. 87.

4. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3398.

5. "The Determination of Stability Constants", 1st ed., 1961, Chapter 5.

If the points, $(1-d, pH_{1-d})$ and $(1+d, pH_{1+d})$ are symmetrically disposed about the point $\bar{x}=1$,

$$pH_{1-d} + pH_{1+d} = 2 pH = K_1, K_2$$

i.e.

$$pH_{1-d} + pH_{1+d} = K_1, K_2$$

where d is the symmetrical distance from the mid-point. It can be easily shown that for the point pH_{1-d} and $1-d$,

$$\log K_1 = pH_{1-d} + \log \left\{ 2(1-d)/d + \sqrt{d^2 + 4(1-d)^2} \frac{K_2}{K_1} \right\} \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

Similarly for the point pH_{1+d} and $1+d$,

$$\log K_2 = pH_{1+d} - \log \left\{ 2(1-d)/d + \sqrt{d^2 + 4(1-d)^2} \frac{K_2}{K_1} \right\} \quad \dots \quad (7)$$

putting $\log \left\{ 2(1-d)/d + \sqrt{d^2 + 4(1-d)^2} \times K_2/K_1 \right\}$ equal to y , equations 6 and 7 may be written as

$$\log K_1 = pH_{1-d} + y \quad \dots \quad (8A)$$

and

$$\log K_2 = pH_{1+d} - y \quad \dots \quad (7A)$$

y may be obtained graphically. The value of the correction term y may also be calculated from the exact equation:

$$y = \log \frac{1-d}{d} + \log \left\{ 1 - \frac{(1+d) L_{1-d}}{(1+d) L_{1+d}} \right\}$$

which is useful in absence of Fig. 1 (p. 3400), if only occasional use is made of the correction term at 'd' values, which are not tabulated". In our case H will be substituted for L in the above equation. The correction term method is applied to observations A, B, C, and J, taking different values of 'd'. Table IV summarises the results obtained in the case of observation A.

TABLE IV

No.	d.	1+d.	1-d.	pH_{1-d} .	pH_{1+d} .	y.	Log K_1 .	Log K_2 .
1	0.2	1.2	0.8	7.82	8.12	-0.0030	8.12	7.82
2	0.3	1.3	0.7	7.74	8.18	-0.1191	8.06	7.86
3	0.4	1.4	0.6	7.64	8.25	-0.1932	8.06	7.83
4	0.5	1.5	0.5	7.55	8.35	-0.2802	8.07	7.83
5	0.6	1.6	0.4	7.40	8.45	-0.3876	8.08	7.77
6	0.7	1.7	0.3	7.27	8.55	-0.5717	7.98	7.84
							Mean 8.06	7.82

The experimental data for the observations B, C, and J were subjected to calculations in the same way. It was noted that in the case of observation J, the order of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ was reversed. The mean of these observations A, B, C, and J was $\log K_1 \pm 0.1 = 7.9$ and $\log K_2 \pm 0.1 = 7.9$.

Least Square Method

According to Irving and Rossotti⁴

$$\bar{n} + (\bar{n}-1) K_1 H + (\bar{n}-2) K_1 K_2 H^2 = 0 \quad \dots (8)$$

$$\frac{\bar{n}}{(\bar{n}-1)H} = \frac{(2-\bar{n})}{(\bar{n}-1)} K_1 K_2 H - K_1 \quad \dots (9)$$

Equation (9) is of the form:

$$y = mx + c, \text{ where } m = K_1 K_2 \text{ and } c = -K_1.$$

Hence, if a graph of $\frac{\bar{n}}{(\bar{n}-1)H}$ against $\frac{(2-\bar{n})H}{(\bar{n}-1)}$ is drawn, K_1 and K_2 may be determined.

Instead of the least square method, a straight line is drawn retaining on it as many points as possible so that positive and negative distances from the points which are not on the line, are approximately equal. The graph of $\bar{n}$ against pH has been drawn (Fig. 2).

From the graph, the values of pH corresponding to the desired values of $\bar{n}$ were read. Data are now available to construct the table, providing the values of

$$\frac{\bar{n}}{(\bar{n}-1)H} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{(2-\bar{n})H}{(\bar{n}-1)}$$

A curve of $\frac{\bar{n}}{(\bar{n}-1)H} \times 10^{-2}$ against $\frac{(2-\bar{n})H}{(\bar{n}-1)} \times 10^2$

FIG. 2

was drawn (Fig. 2). From this curve, the values of $K_1 K_2$ and K_1 can be read. Similar procedure was carried out for the observations B, C, and J. The mean of four observations A, B, C, and J was $\log K_1 \pm 0.1 = 7.0$ and $\log K_2 \pm 0.1 = -7.0$.

Table V summarizes the values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ obtained by different methods.

The results obtained from the maximum number of observations (M.S.A.) may be considered more acceptable. There is, however, no change in the mean values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ even when all the methods are taken into consideration. The mean values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ are 8.0 ± 0.1 and 7.8 ± 0.1 , respectively.

The pK_D values, i. e. the negative logarithm of the dissociation constants, will be $pK_{D_1} = 7.8 \pm 0.1$ and $pK_{D_2} = 8.0 \pm 0.1$. It may be well that $\log K_1 \approx \log K_2$.

TABLE V

Method.	Log $K_1 \pm 0.1$.	Log $K_2 \pm 0.1$.
M.S.A.	8.0	7.8
Spreading factor	8.1	7.7
Correction term	7.9	7.9
Least square	7.9	7.9
Mean	8.0	7.8

It may be concluded that diethyldithiocarbamic acid is a dibasic one, with $pK_{D_1} = 7.8 \pm 0.1$ and $pK_{D_2} = 8.0 \pm 0.1$ (where pK_D terms are the negative logarithm of the dissociation constants). As the two values are fairly close, it is not possible to assign either of the dissociation constants to any particular functional group.

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